

	<p>COMPARATIVE STUDY OF LASER METAL DEPOSITION (LMD) OF COAXIAL WIRE AND POWDER IN THE MANUFACTURE OF TI-6AL-4V STRUCTURES</p>	<p>Industrial Technology</p>
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1.- INTRODUCTION

The additive manufacturing of large titanium aircraft components, typically over 400 mm in length, is an area of work where Direct Energy Deposition (DED) technologies present several advantages over Powder Bed Fusion (PBF) technologies, mainly due to the higher workload of cells and manufacturing machines and the higher input rates of DED technologies [1]. Other widely used DED techniques in the industry include electron beam additive manufacturing (EBAM), wire arc additive manufacturing (WAAM) and laser metal deposition (LMD) [2,3]. The EBAM technique, exclusive to Sciaky, Inc., allows deposition rates of up to 12 kg/h, however, due to the need to generate vacuum and the reduced number of electron beam source suppliers, it is the most expensive technology on the market. On the other hand, WAAM technology is the most economical from an equipment point of view and achieves very high deposition rates of up to approximately 6 kg/h with very good internal material qualities and defectology [4]. In contrast, the limited control of the energy input during manufacture and the high distortions generated in the part should be noted.

The LMD technique outstands from the rest due to the possibility of working with both powder and wire raw material, minimum thermal affection, greater precision and process control, as well as the option of multidirectional deposition. Therefore, the finishes achieved are of good quality, the residual stresses are reduced and consequently the distortions are lower than in the other techniques mentioned. Among the drawbacks of LMD technique are a higher price than WAAM equipment and additive manufacturing feed rates that are, at best, around 4-6 kg/h.

As previously mentioned, within the different variants of the LMD process, it is possible to supply material in both powder and wire form, in both cases in a coaxial way. Each of these methods has its advantages and disadvantages, which are detailed below.

The first advantage of wire is the cost of the material, which is reduced by up to half in most materials. For example, titanium is reduced from 210 €/kg to 100-105 €/kg and Inconel 625 from 84 €/kg to 42-47 €/kg. [5]. Another disadvantage of powder over wire is the risk involved in working with it, both for operators and for the machine itself [6]. Powder particles, which are around 40 - 100µm, can be very hazardous and produce premature and unwanted wear on the machines with which they are used. Even so, it should be noted that both technologies produce gases due to the fusion of metals that are harmful to health.

Finally, the greater efficiency in terms of deposited material that the wire LMD offers as compared to powder must be mentioned. Not all powder is trapped in the molten pool, which reduces the deposition efficiency of the process, typically reaching values close to 70%, in some cases more than 80% depending on the process conditions and the type of nozzle [7,8]. The wire, on the other hand, does not present practically any loss during the deposition.

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If powder is used as a filler, the risk of oxygen or hydrogen contamination (present in the humidity) is greater than with wire, as a result of the higher area/volume ratio of the grains. On the other hand, it is frequent that the powder contains an undesirable distribution of grain, impurities, intragranular pores or non-spherical grain geometries that favour the generation of internal defects in the deposition. This presupposes that the structural characteristics of the wire components are better, since internal defects imply a greater risk of failure generation, mainly for cases of fatigue [9, 10].

The main disadvantage observed in the wire supply is the low process stability associated with narrower focus and focus plane adjustment requirements. In addition, there are geometrical limitations, which are difficult to deal with with this method, such as thin walls or protruding or hollow structures. Finally, it should be noted that process control and automation are more complicated than for powder, which partly explains the lack of commercial wire-based solutions compared to powder supply systems [11].

Among other disadvantages that have been observed with wire feeding are the higher cost of the heads, the impossibility of wire feeding of mixtures of materials or materials with a compositional gradient. On the other hand, the energy contribution is usually higher to melt the wire, which can be especially harmful in materials susceptible to cracking.

The microstructure in the Ti-6Al-4V laser deposition for both wire and powder is quite similar [12]. In summary, titanium acquires the macrostructure of columnar prior β grains, growing epitaxially through different layers in the opposite direction to the heat flow [13]. The border of the prior- β grains is formed by the phase α and the intragranular microstructure varies to some extent from grain to grain. It consists of a fine lamellar structure $\alpha+\beta$, which is mainly found in a structure called basketweave, although the structure of α colonies, which are basically parallel groupings of α plates, is also very frequent. [14]. The size of the colony is limited by the prior- β grain size because its edges are the beginning of nucleation of the plates, these grow until they meet other α colonies or another prior β grain boundary. As the cooling rate increases, the growth of the α colony from the prior β grain boundaries is not fast enough and the plates begin to nucleate at other colony boundaries, thus forming new colonies or at high speeds the basketweave structure [15]. The size of these colonies is essential in the mechanical and fatigue properties because it determines the effective slip length [16,17].

At cooling speeds higher than those required for the formation of the basketweave structure, another phase called martensite α' appears. This is usually very frequent in the first deposited layers, where the cooling is abrupt by the substrate itself [18,19].

In the present article a comparison of the two coaxial variants of LMD technology, the powder and the wire feeding, is made. Coaxial powder feeding is a method developed mainly in the last decade. However, coaxial wire feeding is a new method that is estimated to be more efficient than powder. The main objective of the study is to verify that wire feeder is a method that can achieve higher deposition rates with higher efficiency while maintaining or improving other fundamental aspects such as the geometrical complexity of the components and the microstructure.

First, the materials, equipment and methodology used to carry out the research are shown. Next, the results obtained during the experiment are detailed. Finally, these results are discussed, and the general conclusions of the work are presented.

2.- MATERIALS AND METHOD

Two cells have been used for the deposition of the geometries to be studied, one dedicated to powder LMD and the other to wire LMD. The powder deposition has been carried out using a 2.2 kW continuous wave Nd:YAG laser. The powder has been fed to the molten pool through a

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discrete three-hole coaxial nozzle. The movement of the laser head is provided by a 6-axis robot (Fig. 1a).

In the case of wire, a fibre laser generator (Ytterbium) with a maximum power of 4 kW has been used. The laser beam is guided to the working area through a 600 µm diameter optical fibre, coupled to a three-beam coaxial head. The head is attached to a 6-axis motion robot and a 2-axis positioner (Fig. 1b).

In order to avoid oxidation during the Ti-6Al-4V supply process, a controlled atmosphere chamber has been used, where oxygen is evacuated by introducing pressurised argon. For this purpose, a type of balloon or bag has been used to introduce both the filling head and the part. This chamber, once filled with argon, occupies a space of approximately 500x500x300 mm³, as shown in Fig. 1b.

Fig. 1. Equipment used to make the experiments. Powder cell (a) and wire cell (b)

In order to carry out the deposition rate, efficiency and microstructural analysis, walls of 6-12 mm thickness and 30 mm height have been manufactured, as shown in Fig. 2b. The strategy used for the creation of the walls in both powder and wire form has been a bi-directional strategy alternating 90° from layer to layer. The strategy is shown in Fig. 2a. As soon as the geometric analysis is completed, contributions are added at an angle of 15° with respect to the vertical, in order to determine the geometric limits of the LMD technique.

Fig. 2. Alternate bidirectional strategy used during the manufacture of the walls (a) and deposited walls with powder feeding using the bidirectional strategy(b).

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The process parameters for wall deposition have been chosen according to the highest deposition rates obtained in a parametric search in which the resulting porosity of walls manufactured by different sets of parameters has been analysed. The chosen parameters meet a porosity rate of less than 0.1% and the maximum pore size is 100 μ m. The laser power, the scanning speed and the powder flow or wire feed speed have been selected for the deposition of all the walls, as shown in Table 2.

Feeding format	Power (W)	Scanning speed (mm/s)	Feeding rate (kg/h)	Deposition rate (kg/h)	Energy-mass ratio (MJ/kg)
Powder	2200	20	0.96	0.73	10.85
Wire	2700	25	0.93	0.93	10.45

Table 1. Process parameters used for the manufacture of the walls.

The metallographic preparation for the microstructural analysis was based on sanding with sandpaper from 120pp to 2500pp and a subsequent fine polishing with 0.06 μ m alumina on a polishing cloth. The chemical etching agent used for microstructure evaluation has been Kroll's reagent [20], a dilution of hydrofluoric acid and nitric acid in water.

3.- RESULTS

This section summarizes the results obtained during the experimentation. These results have been divided into the different aspects that have been compared: deposition rate and efficiency, geometric quality and microstructural analysis.

3.1.- Deposition rate and efficiency

The calculation of the efficiency of the deposited material has been made by comparing the total injected mass with the final weight of the deposited pieces. For this purpose, the walls shown in Fig. 2b have been used. First, the walls have been weighed and the weight of the substrate has been subtracted. Equation 1 shows the calculation of the deposited mass.

$$M_{deposited} = 819.36 \text{ g} - 473.13 \text{ g} = 346.23 \text{ g} \quad (1)$$

On the other hand, the deposition time of the 5 walls has been calculated. The time needed to make each layer is 15s and there are five walls of 23 layers, so the total time of deposition has been 28 minutes and 45 s. Both the mass of powder used, and the efficiency have been calculated in equation 2 and equation 3 respectively.

$$M_{feed} = 28.75 \text{ min} \cdot 16 \text{ g/min} = 460 \text{ g} \quad (2)$$

$$Efficiency = \frac{346.23 \text{ g}}{460 \text{ g}} \cdot 100 = 75.3\% \quad (3)$$

With an efficiency of 75.3% the actual deposition rate for powder is 0.72kg/h

Regarding the wire, the efficiency of 100% or very close has been considered, since, as it is a continuous supply of material, all the material melts and is deposited on the walls. The highest rate of deposition used was 7 mm/min with a wire of \varnothing 0.8 mm, resulting in a deposition rate of 0.93 kg/h.

In addition to the deposition rate obtained in the process, the energy-mass ratio of the two feed formats has also been calculated, in order to determine which of the two is more energy efficient. As can be seen in Table 2 this ratio, unlike the state of the art, is very similar, even slightly lower in the case of wire.

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3.2.- Geometric quality

The difference between the two formats of deposition has been analysed in terms of geometry, both complexity and quality and fidelity to the theoretical parts to be manufactured. The versatility of powder technology is greater, and hence its ability to achieve more complex shapes.

As far as vertical walls are concerned, powder has not been a problem, and there is no limit in terms of measurements beyond the range of the robot used for the operation. A prototype wall of 180x80x10 mm is shown in Fig. 3a. A very homogeneous wall with a very stable growth during all the layers is observed, which allows the growth without the use of height control systems. The surface finish is not very good due to the overlapping of beads and the unmelted powder particles that adhere to the beads. However, as these are aeronautical parts, a machining operation is always necessary to avoid fatigue errors.

It must be noted that the substrate has suffered a slight distortion due to the deposition of the wall, in future investigations it is expected to correct this failure with the preheating of the substrate.

On the sharp angle face, as there is no material where the powder can deposit, some of the raw material is lost, thereby reducing efficiency and causing a more jagged finish. In addition, much of this powder is deposited on the substrate forming a mound on the inside of the angle, which is a problem for post machining, as the amount of material to be subtracted is greater.

Fig. 3. Walls of Ti-6Al-4V by powder feeding. Prototype of vertical wall with dimensions 180 x 80 x 10 mm (a). Inclined walls contributed with the head perpendicular to the substrate (b) and with the head parallel to the wall growth (c)

The walls in Fig. 3c, however, have been manufactured with the head tilted in the direction of wall growth. This strategy has allowed an inclined wall to be deposited in the same conditions as the vertical walls and thus equalise efficiency, finish and stability.

These results, combined with a previous study [21] on geometric complexity with steel, allow us to conclude that walls with an angle of up to 55° can be manufactured with Ti-6Al-4V.

The wire deposition has made it more difficult to achieve the desired geometries. The combination of two aspects is fundamental to understand this difficulty. On the one hand, when working with a coaxial feed head, the working range is reduced, close to 0.5mm with respect to the focal plane. On the other hand, 100% of the material is deposited on the wall so instabilities are generated, mainly on the edges where the robot reduces its speed, and on the perimeter that tends to grow less than the inner layer. These instabilities increase with the addition of new layers and are a

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problem for the reduced working range of the head, producing defects when this working range is exceeded. Examples of such instabilities can be seen in Fig. 4a, the height of each wall is limited by the moment the instabilities are too large and a failure in the deposition occurs.

The maximum height achieved is shown in Fig. 4b and c and has been 30 mm. It is necessary to develop strategies and parameters to allow a more stable growth of the layers or to apply a height control to adjust the focal plane to the required height.

Fig. 4. Walls of Ti-6Al-4V by wire deposition. Testing of walls (a) wall with higher height: 30mm (b,c)

As far as surface quality is concerned, the walls have a brighter finish than in the case of powder, mainly because there are no powder particles adhered to the molten material. It should be noted that in cases where the energy input is less than required, jagged shapes appear on the surface.

3.3.- Microstructural analysis

The structure that titanium acquires normally differs in two scale ranges, the macrostructure or intergranular structure, and the microstructure or intragranular structure. Both are relevant since they have direct influence on the mechanical properties of the material.

3.3.1.- Macrostructure

In the study of the macrostructure shown in Fig. 5a, the section of two metallographically prepared walls of Ti-6Al-4V made with powder (a) and wire (b) is observed.

In the case of powder, two main macrostructures are distinguished on each wall. In the lower part, the boundary of the deposited layers can be observed, these are distinguished because in this zone there are high stresses that prevent the chemical etching of the specimens [22]. The prior β grains take on columnar shapes and do not exceed 1mm in thickness. However, in the upper layers there is no differentiation of layers and gradually the grains increase in size and tend to change the shape from columnar to equiaxial.

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These differences in the macrostructure are due to the thermal history. In the first depositions the substrate is at room temperature so there is a very fast heat flow in vertical direction, thus the columnar forms in the direction of heat flow [23]. However, as more layers are added, both the substrate and the previous layers heat up, so this sudden flow does not occur anymore, and the grains acquire more equiaxial forms. Even so, the flow through the wall is greater and therefore the grains are slightly columnar. The generation of higher stresses in the lower layers is the cause of the formation of smaller grains, because these stresses are points of nucleation and grain growth [17,24].

Fig. 5. Sectional view of two walls made by powder (a) and wire (b)

With respect to the parts manufactured with wire feeding, the dynamics of macrostructural formation are the same, however, there are differences due to the different strategies and deposition parameters. In Fig. 5b the section of a wall is observed, and contrary to the previous case, the upper and lower area is not differentiated. This is composed entirely of columnar grains, although a large increase in the size of the grains from the first layer to the rest of the wall is observed. It is understood that the heat flow is much greater, and the appearance of stresses is greater in the first layer than in the others, therefore the creation of smaller grains in the lower zone.

With regard to the lack of equiaxial grains in the upper zone, it must be taken into account that the wire wall has not been deposited continuously, but with a waiting time between layers. These waiting times have allowed the previously deposited material to cool, in such a way that the flow continues to present a marked directionality, following the direction of the wall towards the substrate, thus maintaining the presence of columnar grains. This is also the reason why the separation lines between layers remain visible.

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3.3.2.- Microstructure

The intragranular structure obtained is the usual one in Ti-6Al-4V walls manufactured by additive manufacturing. The same microstructure is found in the deposition of powder and wire. This, as well as the macrostructure, also varies between the lower and upper part of the wall.

In the upper part, the main structure is formed by the primary laminar α phase in a β phase matrix. Depending on the grain the α phase laminates forming colonies or basketweave or Widmanstatten structure (see Fig. 6a and c). These are structures formed by nucleation and diffusion, as the temperature decreases the α phase is formed at the β grain joints and then the plates start to grow inside the grain forming plate colonies in the same direction. However, if the growth rate is high enough, new plates are started from the already growing ones, producing the basketweave structure. The average width of the Widmanstatten plate is $\sim 1.2 \mu\text{m}$ for the case of powder feed and somewhat less for the case of wire, around $1 \mu\text{m}$.

In the lower zone, however, a α' acicular martensitic phase is observed, as shown in Fig. 6b and 6d where more jagged and greyish lamellae are seen. The appearance of this α' martensitic phase is due to a very fast cooling above the temperature of martensitic formation so a transformation by diffusion is impossible. [17,25,26].

Fig. 6. Microstructure obtained on top of both wire(a) and powder(c) specimens: Lamellar structure $\alpha+\beta$ in the form of a "basketweave". Appearance of martensite α' in areas of the lower part close to the substrate in the case of both wire (b) and powder (d) due to faster cooling.

4.- CONCLUSIONS

The work has shown a comparison of wire and powder LMD processes, from a deposition rate, efficiency, geometric and microstructural point of view. It has been observed that the concentric

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wire is a real alternative to the powder supply for the deposition of three-dimensional geometries, although certain deficiencies are observed that require further research.

Of the three aspects analysed, the one referring to deposition rates and efficiency is the most developed in the wire deposition. The maximum rate of deposition is considerably increased, from a rate of 0.73kg/h in powder to 0.93kg/h achieved by wire. Moreover, the use of wire does not involve any loss of material, due to its 100% efficiency, a very big advantage over the 75% achieved in the powder.

With regard to the macrostructure, it can be seen that the one obtained in the process by wire is somewhat worse due to the fact that no previous equiaxial grains have been obtained as is the case with powder. However, this could be improved with continuous deposition and substrate preheating. The microstructure obtained, however, is very similar to that with powder, obtaining a mixed structure of basketweave and α colonies. The basketweave structure is the ideal one because the interlacing of the α plates means a minimum effective slip length. However, the appearance of the colony α increases the slip length to the size of the colony, so this problem has to be addressed by reducing size or converting them to a basketweave structure.

Finally, the geometric aspect of the technology has been studied. The results obtained in the wire deposition are well below the powder mainly due to the instabilities that prevent a correct growth of the walls or parts. This error is expected to be corrected with the use of a height control of the upper surface of the deposited material that allows positioning the head and the focus plane in the correct place. It is also important to deal with the distortions that appear during the process, both in powder and in wire. Although LMD technology is ahead of other technologies in this respect, the reduction of these distortions is very important mainly in the construction of components above 400 mm in length.

Due to the advantage in terms of deposition rate and efficiency and the disadvantage in terms of geometrical complexity, wire input is postulated for the manufacture of components with low geometrical complexity (straight walls, criss-crossed walls or slightly inclined walls) but of large size where the manufacturing time and material expenditure is very high.

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